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Influence of Optical Fiber Sensor Placement on CFRP Laminates for Process and Structural Health Monitoring

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Structural Health Monitoring (SHM)

R. Gondaliya, D. Sypeck, Z. Feng. "Improving Damage Tolerance of Composite Sandwich Structure Subjected to Low Velocity Impact Loading: Experimental Analysis", 31st American Society for Composites, USA, 2016

Increased use of FRP composites on airplanes

- ↑ Mechanical performance by weight ratio
- ↓ Weight
- ↓ Lower fuel consumption & CO₂ emissions
- ↓ Cost

X Difficult to predict failure mechanisms of composites

X Barely Visible Impact Damage (BVID)

✓ Structural Health Monitoring

- Use of embedded or surface mounted sensors
- Increases lifetime of the composite structure
- Repair and maintenance operations in a timely manner, and focused on areas of need

Objectives

- Production of CFRP laminates with embedded FBG sensors by vacuum infusion
- Use of small diameter OF to minimize mechanical properties impairment produced by sensor embedding
- Optimization of OF location for improved damage detectability
- Use of FBG sensors for in-situ cure monitoring and detection of BVID produced by drop weight impact tests

Samples

Quasi-isotropic $[0/45/90/-45/-45/90/45/0]_{2s}$ 4 mm thick (32 layers)

OF Locations in z-axis

↓ 2 mm (mid-plane)

0/45/90/-45/ **OF (C)** /-45/90/45/0/**OF (B)** /0/45/90/-45/-45/90/45/0/**OF (A)** /0/45/90/-45/-45/90/45/0/0/45/90/-45/-45/90/45/0

↑ 0.5 mm ↑ 1 mm

Materials

- Biresin[®] CR83 Composite resin system (hardener 6) from Sika
- Unidirectional Carbon fibre fabric TEX HS 24/150 DLN2 from DYNANO
- 80 μm outer diameter optical fibre from Technicasa

Placement of OF

Prepared preform

Infused preform

Cured laminate

Mechanical Testing

Tensile Testing

Sample	E (GPa)	Ultimate strength (MPa)
NL	43.2 ± 3.2	322.2 ± 53.7
A	41.2 ± 1.6	318.7 ± 63.2
B	40.9 ± 1.7	429.0 ± 6.4
C	44.3 ± 1.7	377.4 ± 34.3

- Load cell: 100 kN
- Test velocity: 2 mm/min

Impact Testing

Cure Monitoring

Wavelength variation of FBG sensors taken during curing under vacuum at room temperature of CFRP laminate produced by VI

Resin Infusion of laminate with FBG containing OF and data acquisition set up

Conclusions

- Although resin pockets were observed in the laminates around the OF, they do not seem to influence the mechanical properties, when comparing the neat laminate with laminates with OF
- Wavelength change of FBG sensors show what seems to be the exothermic peak of curing but the resin is not solid right after that, as it typically happens in standard test methods for determination of gel time and peak exothermic temperature
- Low velocity impact tests will be further used to assess whether FBG sensors can detect BVID

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Thanks for your attention!

